

TEACHING METHODS OF INFORMATICS AND INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY EDUCATION

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Abstract. *The article talks about the role of the computer in the primary education process, the main goals of the primary informatics course, teaching methods in informatics and information technology classes.*

Keywords: *informatics, information technologies, teacher, student, primary class, education, computer, teaching methods.*

Today, the development of information technologies, as well as the widespread introduction of modern information and communication technologies to all areas, especially public administration, education, and health care, are being carried out in our republic. In accordance with the No. PD-357 decree of the President of Uzbekistan dated August 22, 2022 "On measures to take the field of information and communication technologies to a new level in 2022-2023" priority tasks are being implemented [1].

Using the computer as an excellent teaching tool in the educational process has become a way of everyday life. In mathematics, mother tongue and science lessons, the computer becomes a unique assistant of the teacher in many ways. The use of "information technologies" in primary education does not mean the teaching of "basics of information technology" adapted for primary classes, but a comprehensive change of the student's "living environment", a new way for his development and creative activity. creation of tools should be understood [2].

The development of pedagogy, the use of computer and information technologies in teaching, students' thinking, memory, attention, imagination, self-esteem, the ability to plan their actions, and the motivation of primary education subjects in educational activities. increases the possibilities of impact directed at the component.

The main goals of the elementary computer science course in primary education can be briefly formulated as follows:

- forming the beginning of computer literacy;
- development of logical thinking;
- development of algorithmic skills and systematic approaches to solving problems;
- formation of basic computer skills (acquaintance with the computer, basic concepts in the field of information technologies).

The computer is an element that enriches and expands the science environment in the education of elementary school students. Teaching classical informatics to elementary school students, that is, teaching them to receive information presented on the computer screen, mastering the technical capabilities of the computer, logical and algorithmic thinking (correct thinking and planning one's actions) ati) cannot be considered without development. The computer environment significantly facilitates the implementation of psychological and pedagogically based methods using the step-by-step formation of mental actions, which leads not only to increasing the effectiveness of education, but also to accelerating the formation of the ability to independently pose a problem and find a way to solve it. comes [3].

Under the conditions of a normal class-lesson system, teachers successfully use the following teaching methods in computer science and information technology classes in primary education, which makes it possible to effectively build the educational process, taking into account the unique characteristics of the student:

- game method;
- method of group discussion and projects;
- heuristic method;
- explanatory-illustrative method;
- interview method;
- reproductive method;
- method of control and self-control;
- training method;
- training methods;

Game method. In computer classes in the lower grades, the teacher is always forced to create a new, combined type of game based on the role-playing game. The task of the teacher is to help children conduct a mini-performance (role play), the purpose of which is to separate the object from the given set. At the end of the game, the teacher should analyze it.

Group discussion and projects method. In it, the teacher performs leading and coordinating functions. It combines two methods - discussion and project method.

But the project method can also be used as an independent teaching method. The project method is the creation of a result that can be obtained by solving a specific practical or theoretically important problem. This result can be seen, understood and applied in real practical activities.

Starting from the second grade, elements of the project method can be used. When teaching children to work with the Paint graphic editor, they are offered the following tasks: the topic of the drawing they need to create is discussed, and the techniques and tools for doing the work are discussed.

Heuristic method. It is used to develop logical and algorithmic thinking. Students are "passive players". The purpose of the heuristic method is to create a personal educational product (algorithm, fairy tale, program, etc.).

Using the heuristic method, we can distinguish five main stages of organizing students' activities in the lesson:

- motivational (involving all students to discuss familiar algorithms or actions of familiar performers);
- staged (a task is set, students are invited to choose performers who can solve the task);
- creating their own product (students should create their own educational product (with the help of the teacher), as a rule, the algorithm for solving the given problem for the selected performer);
- demonstration (showing students' products in the classroom or in special creative rooms);
- reflective (students evaluate their activity and the result of their work).

Explanation and illustrative method. Clear and coherent explanation of the material. For example, when explaining the performer's work, the teacher uses the interactive whiteboard to show the story and performer's work.

Conversation method. It is used to refresh basic knowledge or to check knowledge to make sure students understand the material correctly.

Reproductive method. Completion and mastering of prepared assignments and tasks.

The method of control and self-control. Use of intermediate and final tests, oral answers.

Exercise method. Solving this problem. Since the thinking of children in primary school is visual-effective and visual-figurative, the entire conceptual apparatus of computer science should be accompanied by exhibitions and experiments. This refers to concepts such as information, information characteristics, information encoding, etc. It helps to better perceive, understand and remember the educational material.

Methods of promotion:

- counting rhymes
- puzzles
- crosswords
- poetry
- puzzles

At the same time, junior schoolchildren easily learn new terms. 15-20 minutes of computer work is enough for mathematics, mother tongue, and science classes. The use of modern information technologies in the field of education allows teachers to qualitatively change the content, methods and organizational forms of education. Information technology itself is combined with a technological process and methods, production processes and software that ensure the collection, storage, processing, output and distribution of information in order to reduce the complexity of the processes of using information resources, increase their reliability and efficiency. can be considered as a set of supplies.

Of course, it can be noted that the computer allows to qualitatively change the control of students' activities while providing flexibility in managing the educational process. The computer allows us to check all the answers, and in most cases it not only notes the error, but also very clearly defines its nature, which helps to eliminate the cause of its occurrence in time. In addition, the computer helps students to develop their personal activities. In the process of working, the computer allows students to imagine the result of their activity, which allows them to draw appropriate conclusions and set educational tasks for the next stage of the lesson.

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